

Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Primary Health Care Physicians Regarding Deprescribing in Older Adults

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Abstract

Background: Polypharmacy is highly prevalent among older adults and is associated with increased risks of adverse drug reactions, drug–drug interactions, and functional decline. Deprescribing has emerged as an important patient-safety strategy in primary care; however, its implementation largely depends on physicians’ knowledge, attitudes, and practices. **Objective:** To assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of primary health care (PHC) physicians regarding deprescribing in older adults and to examine demographic factors associated with these domains. **Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 200 PHC physicians working in Baghdad, Iraq. Data were collected using a structured, pretested electronic questionnaire covering knowledge, attitudes, practices, and perceived barriers and enablers related to deprescribing. Responses were scored and categorized into poor/fair and good levels. **Results:** More than half of participants demonstrated good knowledge of deprescribing (59.0%), while a higher proportion showed good attitudes (77.5%) and good practice (58.0%). Insufficient guidelines (40.5%) and lack of time (31.0%) were the most commonly reported barriers, whereas availability of better guidelines was the main enabler (75.0%). Gender was significantly associated with knowledge ($p = 0.03$), while practice was significantly associated with gender ($p = 0.021$) and years of experience ($p = 0.002$). Physicians with more than 10 years of experience were more likely to demonstrate good deprescribing practice. **Conclusion:** PHC physicians showed generally positive attitudes and acceptable knowledge toward deprescribing, but important gaps in practice remain. Targeted training, clearer guidelines, and practical decision-support tools are needed to strengthen deprescribing implementation and enhance medication safety in older adults.

Introduction

Population ageing and multimorbidity have led to increasingly complex medication regimens in primary care. While multiple medicines may be clinically appropriate, polypharmacy in older adults is consistently linked to higher risks of adverse drug reactions, drug–drug interactions, nonadherence, functional decline, and greater healthcare utilization. A recent narrative review summarizes that these harms are most evident when polypharmacy includes potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs) and when treatment goals are not regularly reassessed in the context of frailty, cognition, and life expectancy [1-3].

Recognizing the global burden of medication-related harm, the World Health Organization highlighted polypharmacy as a key target area within the “Medication Without Harm” initiative and its technical report on medication safety in polypharmacy [2]. In this context, deprescribing has emerged as a core patient-safety and quality-improvement strategy. Deprescribing is commonly defined as the supervised withdrawal (or dose reduction) of an inappropriate medication with the goal of managing polypharmacy and improving outcomes [1]. In older adults, appropriateness is dynamic: a medicine that was once beneficial may become harmful when comorbidities

More Information

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accumulate, renal function declines, or when the time-to-benefit exceeds remaining life expectancy. To identify PIMs and guide safer prescribing, clinicians frequently use explicit tools such as the American Geriatrics Society (AGS) Beers Criteria and STOPP/START criteria [4,5]. These tools support structured medication review, but they do not replace individualized decision-making that considers patient priorities, symptom burden, and the balance of benefit versus harm. Evidence increasingly supports deprescribing interventions in older populations. A recent meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials reported that deprescribing interventions reduce PIMs and adverse drug reactions, and improve several clinical indicators compared with usual care [6]. However, implementation in routine primary care remains challenging. Studies examining physicians' perspectives describe barriers such as limited time, uncertainty about stopping long-term medicines, fear of negative outcomes or conflict with other prescribers, and patient resistance—especially when deprescribing is not supported by clear protocols or shared decision-making tools [7]. Primary health care physicians are central to deprescribing because they coordinate longitudinal care, manage multimorbidity, and reconcile prescriptions from multiple specialists. Assessing physicians' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding deprescribing can identify modifiable gaps (e.g., limited familiarity with deprescribing processes or tools) and inform targeted training, decision-support strategies, and interprofessional models. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the KAP of primary health care physicians regarding deprescribing in older adults and to explore demographic factors associated with these domains.

Method

Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional survey was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of primary health care (PHC) physicians toward deprescribing in older adults. The study was carried out among PHC physicians working in Baghdad and surrounding districts, under the Ministry of Health, Iraq

Study Population and Sampling

The study population comprised PHC physicians who were actively involved in the care of older adults. Inclusion criteria were physicians with at least one year of professional experience in primary health care settings. Physicians who were not involved in the care of older adults were excluded. A convenience sampling technique was used, and a target sample size of approximately 200 physicians was planned to ensure adequate statistical power for analysis.

Inclusion Criteria

Primary health care physicians with at least one year of experience.

Exclusion Criteria

Physicians not involved in the care of older adults.

Data Collection Tool and Procedure

Data were collected using a structured, pretested questionnaire distributed electronically via Google Forms. The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated tools and consisted of four main sections:

1. Knowledge of deprescribing concepts and guidelines,
2. Attitude toward the importance and impact of deprescribing,
3. Practice related to the frequency and approach to deprescribing in routine clinical care, and
4. Perceived barriers and enablers influencing the deprescribing process.

A pilot study involving 20 physicians was conducted to assess clarity and reliability of the questionnaire. Internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, with a value of ≥ 0.7 considered acceptable.

Data Coding and Scoring

Responses were coded numerically in Microsoft excel, Knowledge, attitude and practicing items were coded using scored positive response=2, while nutrient response=1 and negative response=0. Knowledge, attitude and practicing scores $\leq 50\%$ were classified as poor to fair [8].

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, with categorical variables presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between demographic variables and knowledge, attitude, and practice were examined using the chi-square test, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Arab board of health specializations Research Ethics Committee.

Results

The study included 200 participants, predominantly female (74.5%), reflecting the gender distribution of the target workforce. Most participants were aged 35–44 years (40.5%), followed by 25–34 years (33.0%), indicating a largely young to middle-aged cohort. Experience was almost evenly distributed, with 51.0% having ≤ 10 years and 49.0% having > 10 years of practice. The majority of participants were Family Medicine specialists (90.5%), confirming that the sample was highly representative of primary care physicians. 40% of participants have Insufficient guidelines as barriers followed by 31% of them have Lack of time. 50% of participant have Better guidelines as Enablers. As in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Study Sample According to Demographic

Variable	Category	No.	%
Sex	Female	149	74.5
	Male	51	25.5
Age (years)	25 -34	66	33.0
	35 - 44	81	40.5
	45 - 54	39	19.5
	55 - 64	14	7.0
Experience years	>10	98	49.0
	≤10	102	51.0
Specialty	Family medicine	181	90.5
	Other	19	9.5
	Fear of negative health outcomes	20	10.0
Barriers	Insufficient guidelines	81	40.5
	Lack of support from colleagues	7	3.5
	Lack of time	62	31.0
	Patient resistance	30	15.0
	Better guidelines	150	75.0
Enablers	More education and training	36	18.0
	Patient education	8	4.0
	Support from specialists	6	3.0
Total		200	100

Overall, the findings indicate a high proportion of favorable outcomes in key domains. More than half of the participants demonstrated good knowledge (59.0%). Attitude was exhibiting good attitude (77.5%), suggesting positive perceptions and readiness toward the subject under study. Practice also showed a 58.0% of participants reported good practice. As in table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Study Sample According to Knowledge, Attitude and Practice

Variable	Category	No.	%
Knowledge	Poor	82	41.0
	Good	118	59.0
Attitude	Poor	45	22.5
	Good	155	77.5
Practice	Poor	84	42.0
	Good	116	58.0
Total		200	100

Regarding age, participants aged 35–44 years constituted the largest proportion among those with good knowledge (43.2%), followed by the 45–54 year age group (20.3%). In contrast, the 25–34 year group

accounted for a higher proportion of those with poor knowledge (41.5%). However, the overall association between age group and knowledge level was not statistically significant ($p = 0.1$). A statistically significant association was observed between gender and knowledge level ($p = 0.03$). Females represented the majority in both knowledge categories; however, males showed a relatively higher proportion of good knowledge (31.4%) compared with poor knowledge (17.1%). With respect to years of experience, participants with ≤ 10 years of practice contributed slightly more to the poor knowledge group (53.7%), while those with > 10 years of experience were marginally more represented in the good knowledge group (50.8%). Nonetheless, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.5$). Regarding specialty, most participants in both poor and good knowledge categories were from Family Medicine. Although participants from other specialties had a higher proportion of good knowledge (11.9%) compared to poor knowledge (6.1%), the association between specialty and knowledge level was not statistically significant ($p = 0.2$). as in table 3.

Table 3: Association between Variable Demographic and Knowledge

Age Group (years)	Knowledge		P-value
	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	
25–34	34 (41.5%)	32 (27.1%)	0.1
35–44	30 (36.6%)	51 (43.2%)	
45–54	15 (18.3%)	24 (20.3%)	
55–64	3 (3.7%)	11 (9.3%)	
Gender	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value

Female	68 (82.9%)	81 (68.6%)	0.03
Male	14 (17.1%)	37 (31.4%)	
Experience years	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value 0.5
>10 years	38 (46.3%)	60 (50.8%)	
≤10 years	44 (53.7%)	58 (49.2%)	
Specialist	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value 0.2
Family Medicine	77 (93.9%)	104 (88.1%)	
Other specialties	5 (6.1%)	14 (11.9%)	

Regarding age, participants aged 35–44 years constituted the largest proportion of those with a good attitude (40.6%), followed by the 25–34 year group (31.0%). Conversely, the 25–34 and 35–44 year age groups each accounted for 40.0% of participants with a poor attitude. Despite these variations, the association between age group and attitude was not statistically significant ($p = 0.6$). However, males accounted for a relatively higher proportion of the good attitude group (28.4%) compared with the poor attitude group (15.6%). This difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.1$). With respect to years of

experience, participants with ≤10 years of practice contributed more to the poor attitude group (57.8%), whereas those with >10 years of experience were more frequently represented in the good attitude group (51.0%). Nevertheless, this association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.3$). Although participants from other specialties showed a slightly higher proportion of good attitude (10.3%) compared to poor attitude (6.7%), the association between specialty and attitude was not statistically significant ($p = 0.5$). as in table 4.

Table 4: Association between Variable Demographic and Attitude

Age Group (years)	Attitude		P-value
	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	
25–34	18 (40.0%)	48 (31.0%)	0.6
35–44	18 (40.0%)	63 (40.6%)	
45–54	7 (15.6%)	32 (20.6%)	
55–64	2 (4.4%)	12 (7.7%)	
Gender	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value 0.1
Female	38 (84.4%)	111 (71.6%)	
Male	7 (15.6%)	44 (28.4%)	
Experience years	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value 0.3
>10 years	19 (42.2%)	79 (51.0%)	
≤10 years	26 (57.8%)	76 (49.0%)	
Specialist	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value 0.5
Family Medicine	42 (93.3%)	139 (89.7%)	
Other specialties	3 (6.7%)	16 (10.3%)	

Regarding age, participants aged 35–44 years represented the largest proportion of those with good practice (42.2%), followed by the 45–54 year group (23.3%). In contrast, the 25–34 year age group accounted for the highest proportion of poor practice (42.9%). The association between age group and practice was borderline statistically significant ($p = 0.05$). A statistically significant association was observed between gender and practice ($p = 0.021$). Females constituted the majority of both practice categories; however, males were proportionally more represented in the good practice group (31.9%) compared with the poor practice group (16.7%). With

respect to years of experience, a strong and statistically significant association was identified ($p = 0.002$). Participants with >10 years of experience were markedly more likely to demonstrate good practice (58.6%), whereas those with ≤10 years of practice predominated in the poor practice group (64.3%). Regarding specialty, most participants in both poor and good practice categories were from Family Medicine. Although participants from other specialties showed a higher proportion of good practice (12.1%) compared to poor practice (6.0%), the association between specialty and practice was not statistically significant ($p = 0.2$). as in table 5.

Table 5: Association between Variable Demographic and Practice

Age Group (years)	Practice		P-value
	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	
25–34	36 (42.9%)	30 (25.9%)	0.05
35–44	32 (38.1%)	49 (42.2%)	
45–54	12 (14.3%)	27 (23.3%)	
55–64	4 (4.8%)	10 (8.6%)	
Gender	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value
Female	70 (83.3%)	79 (68.1%)	0.021
Male	14 (16.7%)	37 (31.9%)	
Experience years	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value
>10 years	30 (35.7%)	68 (58.6%)	0.002
≤10 years	54 (64.3%)	48 (41.4%)	
Specialist	Poor (No. %)	Good (No. %)	P-value
Family Medicine	79 (94.0%)	102 (87.9%)	0.2
Other specialties	5 (6.0%)	14 (12.1%)	

Discussion

This study provides important insights into the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of primary health care physicians regarding deprescribing in older adults. Overall, the findings demonstrate a generally favorable profile, particularly in attitude and practice, while also revealing critical gaps that may hinder optimal deprescribing implementation in routine primary care. The demographic characteristics of the participants indicate that the study population was largely representative of the primary care workforce, with a predominance of female physicians and family medicine specialists. Similar workforce distributions have been reported in primary care studies across different regions, reflecting the central role of family physicians in managing older adults with multimorbidity [9]. The predominance of physicians in the 35–44 year age group suggests a relatively young to middle-aged cohort, which may influence clinical confidence and decision-making related to deprescribing. In terms of knowledge, more than half of the participants demonstrated good knowledge (59.0%), indicating an acceptable level of awareness of deprescribing principles. However, the presence of poor knowledge in 41.0% of physicians highlights a substantial gap. Comparable levels of knowledge have been reported in studies from primary care settings in Asia and the Middle East, where physicians often acknowledge deprescribing concepts but lack structured training or guideline familiarity [10,11]. In the present study, gender was the only demographic variable significantly associated with knowledge, with male physicians demonstrating better knowledge levels. While similar findings have been observed in some studies [12], others have found no gender-based differences, suggesting that contextual factors and access to continuing medical education may play a more important role [13].

Attitude toward deprescribing was notably positive, with 77.5% of physicians exhibiting good attitude, reflecting strong recognition of the importance of deprescribing in older adults. This finding aligns with international literature showing that most physicians support deprescribing as a strategy to reduce polypharmacy and adverse drug events [14,15]. The absence of significant associations between attitude and demographic variables indicates that favorable perceptions toward deprescribing are consistently shared across age groups, genders, experience levels, and specialties, a pattern similarly reported in previous primary care studies [11,16]. In contrast, practice showed the strongest demographic associations. Although 58.0% of physicians reported good practice, a substantial proportion still demonstrated poor deprescribing practices. Age showed a borderline significant association with practice, suggesting improvement with increasing age. More importantly, years of experience were strongly associated with good practice, with physicians having more than 10 years of experience being significantly more likely to deprescribe appropriately. This finding is consistent with previous research indicating that clinical experience enhances physicians’ confidence in medication review, shared decision-making, and risk-benefit assessment [14,17]. Gender was also significantly associated with practice, with male physicians demonstrating better practice patterns, a finding reported in some but not all studies [12,18]. Specialty was not significantly associated with practice, emphasizing that experience rather than specialty background is a key determinant of effective deprescribing. General, the findings highlight a clear knowledge–attitude–practice gap, where positive attitudes do not consistently translate into optimal practice. This underscores the need for targeted training programs, practical deprescribing tools, and continuous medical education initiatives, particularly

for younger and less experienced physicians, to enhance deprescribing implementation and improve medication safety in older adults.

Conclusion

Primary health care physicians demonstrated favorable attitudes and moderate knowledge toward deprescribing in older adults, yet practical application remains suboptimal. Experience played a significant role, with more experienced physicians showing better deprescribing practices. Persistent barriers, particularly insufficient guidelines and limited time, continue to hinder effective implementation. Strengthening training programs and providing clear, practical deprescribing guidelines are essential to improve medication safety in older populations.

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